

Oral Presentation #33 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Gokhan Zaim
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0676-8540>

Cagri Akalin
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3370-9879>

AFFILIATIONS

Ordu University
Ordu, Turkey

Ordu University
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Splenic artery aneurysms are the most common among visceral artery aneurysms, with an incidence of 0.1-0.2%. The rupture of splenic artery aneurysms is a rare condition with a high mortality rate (25-75%). We present the course of a rare case of spontaneous ruptured splenic artery aneurysm with a high mortality risk.

Case Presentation: Our patient is a 60-year-old male who presented to a district state hospital with complaints of sudden onset abdominal pain radiating to the back. Computed tomography revealed a splenic artery aneurysm rupture, and he was referred to our clinic via the 112-emergency coordination center. The patient was received in the emergency room. The patient was quickly taken to surgery. Following splenectomy, the splenic artery was ligated proximally and distally.

Splenectomy allowed better hemorrhage control. Except for delirium in the postoperative period in the ICU (intensive care unit), no complications were noted. During long-term follow-up, the patient developed an incisional hernia and underwent surgery for it in the eighth month. Our patient is healthy and has no complaints at the 15th month controls.

Conclusion: Our patient, who presented with a ruptured splenic artery aneurysm, recovered with emergency laparotomy. In hemodynamically unstable patients with splenic artery aneurysm rupture, emergency laparotomy is life-saving.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Aneurysm, ruptured, diagnosis, splenectomy, splenic artery, hernia, delirium

INTRODUCTION

Splenic artery aneurysms are the most common among visceral artery aneurysms, with an incidence of 0.1-0.2%. The rupture of splenic artery aneurysms is a rare condition with a high mortality rate (25-75%). We present the course of a rare case of spontaneous ruptured splenic artery aneurysm with a high mortality risk.

CASE PRESENTATION

Our patient is a 60-year-old male who presented to a district state hospital with complaints of sudden onset abdominal pain radiating to the back. Computed tomography revealed a splenic artery aneurysm rupture, and he was referred to our clinic via the 112-emergency coordination center. The patient was received in the emergency room. He was conscious but appeared highly agitated. He reported severe pain radiating to his left shoulder and back, stating that he was unable to tolerate it. He had no history of smoking or known comorbidities. He had no history of regular medication use. On physical examination, the pulse was 88 beats per minute, and arterial blood pressure was 85/50 mmHg. The epigastric region was defensive. Hemoglobin level measured in the emergency department was 8.2 mg/dl. CT showed an organized hematoma around the ruptured splenic artery and free fluid in the perihepatic area (Image 1).

Image 1

Yellow arrow; hematomas, white arrow; ruptured splenic artery aneurysm

About 40 minutes had passed since the CT was taken. The patient was quickly taken to surgery. A large hematoma extending beyond the lesser omentum and filling the left upper quadrant was evacuated. The lesser omentum was opened and the hematoma in that area was also cleared. It was difficult to access the bleeding site and spleen. Compresses were placed on the actively bleeding area. To increase exposure, the incision was extended to the left subcostal region. Following splenectomy, the splenic artery was ligated proximally and distally. Splenectomy allowed better hemorrhage control. The patient received 3 units of erythrocyte suspension. His hemoglobin was 9.1 mg/dl at discharge. Except for delirium in the postoperative period in the ICU (intensive care unit), no complications were noted. He was discharged on the 7th postoperative day. Pneumococcal, meningococcal, and Haemophilus influenza type B vaccines were administered in the second week after discharge. During long-term follow-up, the patient developed an incisional hernia and underwent surgery for it in the eighth month. Our patient is healthy and has no complaints at the 15th month control.

Ethics Committee Approval: As this is a case report, ethics committee approval was not required. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

DISCUSSION

Splenic artery aneurysm was first described by Beaussier in 1770 (Beaussier, 1770). Its prevalence in the population is 0.09% in autopsy series and 0.78% in arteriographic studies (Stanley, Thompson, & Fry, 1970). Visceral artery aneurysms represent 5% of intra-abdominal aneurysms, and the most common type is splenic artery aneurysms, comprising 60% (Chaer et al., 2020; Marone et al., 2011a). These aneurysms are four times more common in women, but the risk of rupture is higher in men (Ierardi et al., 2014). Etiological factors for splenic artery aneurysms include atherosclerosis, medial degeneration, dysplasia, infection and inflammatory diseases, connective tissue disorders, portal hypertension, pregnancy, and iatrogenic causes related to interventional procedures (Marone et al., 2011b). Risk factors for rupture include pregnancy and portal hypertension, which leads to medial hyperplasia and fragmentation of the elastic lamina in the arterial wall (Pararas et al., 2020). Our patient had no comorbidities, history of smoking, or trauma. Endovascular, open surgical, and laparoscopic approaches have all been shown to be effective in the treatment of splenic artery aneurysms (Arca et al., 1999; Chaer et al., 2020). Although successful endovascular interventions for splenic

artery aneurysm rupture have been reported in recent years, open surgical ligation of the splenic artery, with or without splenectomy, remains the first-line treatment (Chaer et al., 2020; Rinaldi, Brioschi, & Marone, 2023). Aneurysm rupture leads to hemodynamic instability and requires urgent transfer to the operating room (Chaer et al., 2020). Typically, the rupture occurs in two stages. In the first stage, the hemorrhage fills the lesser omentum, and the tamponade effect of the hematoma provides temporary control. This phase buys time for intervention. In the second stage, the hemorrhage overcomes the lesser omentum, making hemodynamic stabilization difficult (Pararas et al., 2020). In our patient's CT, there was free hematoma around the liver and spleen, indicating the second stage. We performed emergency laparotomy. There was hematoma in the abdomen, around the spleen and liver, and filling the lesser omentum. Ligation of the splenic artery with splenectomy allowed us to control the bleeding. The patient was monitored in the ICU postoperatively. On postoperative day 4, he developed delirium. Delirium is seen in 70–87% of ICU patients (Ely et al., 2001). It may have been triggered by a high-risk condition at admission, lack of sunlight, absence of visitors, medications, or other causes (Ali & Cascella, 2025).

The condition resolved within 24 hours with psychiatric support after transfer to the ward. In the sixth postoperative month, a whole-body CT angiography showed no aneurysms elsewhere in the body, especially intracranial. An incisional hernia developed and was repaired with a retromuscular mesh graft in the eighth month. Patients with previous abdominal surgery have a 10% risk of hernia development, and repair with retromuscular mesh is recommended (Sanders et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

Our patient, who presented with a ruptured splenic artery aneurysm, recovered with emergency laparotomy. In hemodynamically unstable patients with splenic artery aneurysm rupture, emergency laparotomy is life-saving.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Ali, M., & Cascella, M. (2025, January). ICU delirium. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559280/>
- Arca, M. J., Gagner, M., Heniford, B. T., Sullivan, T. M., & Beven, E. G. (1999). Splenic artery aneurysms: Methods of laparoscopic repair. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 30(1), 184–188. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0741-5214\(99\)70190-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0741-5214(99)70190-4)
- Beaussier, M. (1770). Sur un anévrisme de l'artère splénique: dont les parois se sont ossifiées. *Journal de Médecine de Toulouse*, 32, 157–162.
- Chaer, R. A., Abularrage, C. J., Coleman, D. M., Eslami, M. H., Kashyap, V. S., Rockman, C., & Murad, M. H. (2020). The Society for Vascular Surgery clinical practice guidelines on the management of visceral aneurysms. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 72(1 Suppl), 3S–39S. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2020.01.039>
- Ely, E. W., Inouye, S. K., Bernard, G. R., Gordon, S., Francis, J., May, L., ... & Dittus, R. (2001). Delirium in mechanically ventilated patients: Validity and reliability of the Confusion Assessment Method for the Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU). *JAMA*, 286(21), 2703–2710. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.286.21.2703>
- Ierardi, A. M., Petrillo, M., Bacuzzi, A., Floridi, C., Dionigi, G., Piffaretti, G., & Carrafiello, G. (2014). Endovascular retreatment of a splenic artery aneurysm refilled by collateral branches of the left gastric artery: A case report. *Journal of Medical Case Reports*, 8, Article 436. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1752-1947-8-436>
- Marone, E. M., Mascia, D., Kahlberg, A., Brioschi, C., Tshomba, Y., & Chiesa, R. (2011). Visceral artery aneurysms and pseudoaneurysms—Should they all be managed by endovascular techniques? *Annals of Vascular Surgery*, 25(7), 936–946. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avsg.2011.03.006>

Pararas, N., Rajendiran, S., Taha, I., Powar, R. R., Holguera, C., & Tadros, E. (2020). Spontaneous rupture of a huge splenic artery aneurysm: A case report. *American Journal of Case Reports*, 21, e919956. <https://doi.org/10.12659/AJCR.919956>

Rinaldi, L. F., Brioschi, C., & Marone, E. M. (2023). Endovascular and open surgical treatment of ruptured splenic artery aneurysms: A case report and a systematic literature review. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(18), 6085. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12186085>

Sanders, D. L., Pawlak, M. M., Simons, M. P., Aufenacker, T., Balla, A., Berger, C., ... & Stabilini, C. (2023). Midline incisional hernia guidelines: The European Hernia Society. *British Journal of Surgery*, 110(12), 1732–1768. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjs/znad284>

Stanley, J. C., Thompson, N. W., & Fry, W. J. (1970). Splanchnic artery aneurysms. *Archives of Surgery*, 101(6), 689–697. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archsurg.1970.01340300045009>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Gokhan Zaim

Ordu University

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0676-8540>

drgzaim@gmail.com